

METHODOLOGY COMPUTER SIMULATION OF DEMONSTRATION EXPERIMENTS ON DIFFRACTION OF LIGHT, X-RAYS AND ELECTRONS FOR PHYSICISTS

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Abstract

A Mathematica-based computer demonstration experiment is designed to demonstrate the diffraction of light, X-ray, and electron waves on different media—an ordinary two-dimensional optical diffraction grating and a three-dimensional crystal. It is shown that in spite of the cardinal differences of these media in their nature and interaction with radiation, the phenomenon of diffraction of electromagnetic and electron waves is considered from a unified point of view.

Key words: demonstration experiment, computer experiment, Fraunhofer diffraction, slot diffraction, computer algebra system

Attention to education in our country is growing day by day. In order to further develop the education system and provide education on an equal basis with developed countries, the higher education system in our country is gradually switching to training using a credit-modular system.

Optics are special disciplines for students of physical specialties of the higher education system. Computer technology is important in explaining their satisfaction. It also has the ability to solve equations, draw graphs, create models and much more using the Mathematica package[1,2,3].

Looking at world experience, scientific work has been carried out on the use of computer technology in teaching optics to demonstrate patterns, obtain results in laboratory work, reinforce topics, and conduct intermediate and final controls. In their work, the method of demonstrating patterns corresponds to our scientific work.

In the optics section of the general physics course, students study the phenomena of interference and diffraction of light. In this case, the main attention is paid to Fraunhofer diffraction by slits and diffraction gratings. In such cases, as a rule, the presentation of the question is based on the basic position in which the image given by the lens is always a diffraction pattern arising due to the limitation of the cross section of the light beam. Mathematical analysis of many interesting examples of Fraunhofer diffraction is not difficult and allows us to consider the problem at hand.

The study of the phenomenon of light diffraction by slits and two-dimensional diffraction gratings is a relatively simple task, in which the equality of phases and the equality of amplitudes incident on the diffraction grating and other obstacles greatly simplifies both the graphical and analytical solution of the problem for certain geometries of the chosen experimental scheme [1-3].

The study of X-ray diffraction, for which the role of an ordinary diffraction grating is played by crystalline bodies, is a relatively difficult task due to their interaction with a specific object. Here, processes such as the interaction of X-rays with individual atoms of matter and the symmetry of the arrangement of atoms in a crystal come to the fore. In the first case, we are dealing with the atomic factor, and in the second case with the structural scattering factor, which have a significant effect on the intensity of the diffracted rays. Along with this, during the diffraction of X-rays, it is necessary to pay attention to the condition characteristic of them, according to which the distance between the atomic planes d , the wavelength λ and the diffraction angle θ are related by the Bragg condition $2d \sin \theta = n\lambda$ (n - diffraction order). Here, for the occurrence of the X-ray diffraction maximum, the difference in the path of the rays $d \sin \theta$ is $\lambda/2$, and for light, the difference in the path of the rays is λ . However, when determining the total amplitude of the diffracted light and X-ray radiation, the usual procedure for adding the amplitudes of the radiation scattered in each section of the diffraction grating is performed. The intensity is defined as the product of the calculated amplitude and the conjugate value. Both in conventional optics and in X-ray diffraction, the nature of the intensity of scattered radiation near the maximum in the one-dimensional case is given by an expression like:

$$I_{\varphi} = k \frac{\sin^2[(b\pi/\lambda) \sin \varphi]}{[(b\pi/\lambda) \sin \varphi]^2}. \quad (1)$$

In the case of light, the coefficient k is the intensity of light coming from a slit wide b in the direction of the primary beam. At the same time, for X-rays k it also depends mainly on the atomic and structural scattering factors. The φ angle between the scattered and primary beams is denoted by.

Naturally, the processes of interaction between the electron wave and the electrons of the crystal significantly complicate the material under study. As a result, they resort to the study of thin crystalline foil with a thickness not exceeding microns. Short X-ray waves are used, corresponding to a voltage between the anode and the cathode, in many cases equal to 100,000 volts ($\lambda = 0,0370 \text{ \AA}$). Consequently, it is practically necessary to work with wavelengths that are much smaller than the interplanar distances in the crystal and with

small diffraction angles. Along with this, a detailed interpretation of electron micrographs and electron diffraction patterns possible only at complete understanding physical factors determining intensity Bragg diffracted beams. Therefore, in practice one should consistently calculate amplitude scattering on an atom, elementary cell and on crystal at provided that amplitude scattered waves is only small part amplitude falling waves.

We note that when considering the phenomenon of diffraction in crystals, it is very useful to deal with the reciprocal lattice of a crystal, the presentation of the principle of construction of which is not a difficult task. In this case, g a c^* strong h, k, l diffraction a^* maximum $|\mathbf{K}| = 2 \frac{\sin \theta}{\lambda}$, arises b^* under the condition $\mathbf{K} = \mathbf{g} = ha^* + kb^* + lc^*$ $|\mathbf{g}| = \frac{1}{d_{hkl}}$, d_{hkl} - interplanar distance. In its physical meaning, the vector $\mathbf{K}$ corresponds to the wave vector. It is natural to assume that in the case $\mathbf{K} = \mathbf{g} + \mathbf{s}$ where $\mathbf{s}$ represents the deviation from the reciprocal lattice node, one can expect a non-zero amplitude of the diffracted radiation. In this case, for the amplitude of the scattered radiation, the expression $A_g = \frac{F_g}{V_c} \int \exp[-2\pi i \mathbf{s} \cdot \mathbf{r}] d\tau$ containing the integral over the crystal is obtained, which is the Fourier transform of the crystal. F_g - structural factor, V_c - unit cell volume. For a rectangular crystal with edges A, B and C this expression has the form:

$$|A_g| = \frac{F_g}{V_c} \cdot \frac{\sin \pi A u}{\pi u} \cdot \frac{\sin \pi B v}{\pi v} \cdot \frac{\sin \pi C w}{\pi w}. \quad (2)$$

Here u, v, w , are the components $\mathbf{s}$ along the directions, respectively x, y, z . The value $|A_g|$ characterizes the distribution of amplitudes in the reciprocal space. As noted above, the distribution of the intensity of the diffracted beam is determined by the product Here, we assume $A_g A_g^*$. that the values of the type $\frac{F_g}{V_c}$ are constant and equal to unity. Naturally, to solve such problems and to study courses in general and theoretical physics, a relatively solid mathematical background is required.

Now, in accordance with the above reasoning, we can start modeling light on a two-dimensional diffraction grating, X-rays and electron beams in crystalline bodies based on a single computer simulation. We use the Mathematica computer algebra system, with which we constantly used in our previous works [4-5].

Let us compose expressions for visualizing the results of calculations according to formula (1) for the two-dimensional case, we will write the following expression for Mathematica:

$$\text{ContourPlot} \left[\frac{F}{V} \left(\frac{\text{Sin}[\pi a x]}{\text{Pi } x} \right)^2 \left(\frac{\text{Sin}[\text{Pi } b y]}{\text{Pi } x} \right)^2, \{x, 0.5, 5\}, \{y, 0.5, 5\} \right].$$

The $\frac{F}{V} = 1$ result of the calculations will be the picture shown in Fig. 1. The resulting picture is a fragment of the reciprocal lattice in the plane (x, y) . Profiles of reciprocal lattice sites are seen, the cross sections of which depend on the values of x and y , which corresponds to a decrease in the intensity of diffracted radiation depending on the diffraction angle. However, the distances between the nodes of the reciprocal lattice do not change and depend only on a and b . Now we can demonstrate the change in the intensity of diffracted radiation in one direction to increase the visibility of the phenomenon under study (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. Fragment of the section of the reciprocal lattice in the plane (xy) .

Fig. 2. Intensity distribution of the diffracted wave along A.

Mathematica allows you to manipulate the parameters used directly during the demonstration experiment. So, for example, to use a two-dimensional diffraction pattern, you can get the picture shown in Fig. 3. Here it is possible to change the width of the slit b and the number of slits n directly during the demonstration of a computer experiment. To get the desired result, enter the command:

$$\text{Manipulate} \left[\text{Plot} \left[\left\{ \left(\frac{\text{Sin} \left[\frac{\pi b}{\lambda} \text{Sin}[\varphi] \right]}{\frac{\pi b}{\lambda} \text{Sin}[\varphi]} \right)^2, \left(\frac{\text{Sin} \left[n \frac{\pi b}{\lambda} \text{Sin}[\varphi] \right]}{n \frac{\pi b}{\lambda} \text{Sin}[\varphi]} \right)^2 \right\}, \{\varphi, 0, 1\} \right], \{b, 0.001, 0.06\}, \{n, 1, 10\}, \text{PlotRange} \rightarrow \{0, 0.5\} \right]$$

The conducted studies have shown that the above computer demonstrations can also be used to illustrate other schemes of diffraction experiments, for example, to show the superposition of sound waves, as well as waves propagating on the surface of water. We believe that the proposed development should primarily be used during lectures and independent work of students and undergraduates.

Использованная литература:

1. P.V. Kazarin, Yu.V. Polushtaitsev, N.F. Uslugin. Lecture experiments on the demonstration of light diffraction in the system of university physical education. Bulletin of the Nizhny Novgorod University. N.I. Lobachevsky. Series: Social Sciences, 2017, No. 3 (47), p. 143–147.
2. Lecture demonstrations in physics / Ed. V.I. Iveronova. M.: Nauka, 1972. 640 p.
3. Maciej Lisicki, Ludmila Buller, Michal Oszmaniec, Krzysztof Wojtowicz. Dynamic transition between Fresnel and Fraunhofer diffraction patterns - a lecture experiment. arXiv:0803.0120v2 [physics.optics] 22 Apr 2009.
- 4 Stephen Wolfram. An Elementary Introduction to the Wolfram Language. second edition. Champaign, IL, USA: Wolfram Media, Inc. 2017. 339 p.
5. Gerd Baumann. Mathematica for theoretical physics. 2. Electrodynamics, quantum mechanics, general relativity, and fractals. Springer. 2005. 942p .
6. G.Z. Babakhova Computer simulation of demonstration experiments on the diffraction of light, X-rays and electrons for undergraduate and graduate students in physics//Berlin Studies Transnational Journal of Science and Humanities ISSN 2749-0866 Vol.2 Issue 1.5 Pedagogical sciences <http://berlinstudies.de/> 974-979 p